

Early Season Corn Acreage Estimates in the Presence of Extreme Weather

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Abstract

The United States Department of Agriculture National Agricultural Statistics Service (NASS) provides timely and accurate statistics in service to U.S. agriculture. An example includes planted acreage estimates for corn. NASS conducts surveys in March and June to provide early season estimates of corn acreage. Since planting typically occurs in May and June, farmers are generally reporting planting intentions in March. Information collected during the first ten days of June through the June Agricultural Survey is typically a close representation of what is planted since corn planting generally is complete by the end of June. It is possible, however, that planting can be prevented by extreme weather. If this is the case, the June Agricultural Survey may still include planting intentions, which can bias the results when intentions are changed due to weather conditions. More information is necessary to mitigate this potential source of bias. The objective of this study is to use machine learning to combine the June survey estimate with precipitation, temperature, economic and other data to forecast corn planted acreage. The accuracies of the model estimates are measured based on the relative error with respect to end-of-season official acreages.

Key Words: Machine Learning, Agriculture, Anomaly Detection

1. Introduction

The United States Department of Agriculture's (USDA's) National Agricultural Statistics Service (NASS) reports estimates of acreage planted to a variety of crops throughout the growing season. Consumers of these statistics include farmers and ranchers for planning and market assessment, federal and state agencies for research and decision-making, and internal USDA stakeholders. NASS planted acreage statistics are the result of an expert review process that is conducted under the direction of the NASS Agricultural Statistics Board (ASB). These board-acreage estimates are published at various geographic levels at the end of March, June, and December. The March and June estimates are forecasts, informed by surveys conducted during those months. The December estimates are considered final. The focus of this research is to improve the quality of the June planted acreage estimates for corn.

The June corn estimates are typically very accurate with respect to the final published acreages in December. The accuracy comes from the fact that corn planting is usually nearing completion when the survey is administered. Sometimes the survey estimates can be affected by delayed planting conditions, such as those caused by excessive precipitation. If it is too wet to plant, farmers may report corn they intend to plant, as opposed to corn already planted. Continued poor weather conditions may prevent farmers from planting what they recorded on the survey, which would potentially impact the quality of the survey estimates. Therefore, it is desirable to have a method of adjusting the survey estimates to improve accuracy when adverse weather events impact planned plantings while maintaining accuracy during normal seasons.

When adverse weather events disrupt planting, NASS sometimes conducts a survey in July and adjusts the June Agricultural Survey estimates. Since resurveys involve added expense and respondent burden, a reduced cost, automated approach is desirable. This paper proposes a regression-based machine learning approach to accomplish adjustment of June Agricultural Survey forecasts during excessively wet years. A planted acreage model is fit at the county-level using gradient boosting with the official county level corn acreage regressed on survey summaries, weather, and economic data. The modeled acreage forecasts perform competitively with the June ASB forecast when evaluated against the final official values during years where resurveys were required.

1.1 Previous Work

Several modeling strategies have been used in the literature to forecast planted acreage for varying stages in the cropping season. To be useful for adjusting the June Agricultural Survey forecasts, the model must use data available up to and no later than early to mid-June. Modeling strategies for planted area that can be deployed in June or earlier are discussed here.

Time series methods, where historical planted areas are used to predict the current area, are common (El-Khalifa et al., 2022; Savadatti, 2017; Tripathi et al., 2014). At field-level scale, a time series of historical crop rotations can be used to predict the current year's crop type, with the crop types summed to the desired area of interest (Zhang et al., 2019).

External covariates can also be included to improve predictions. Like the time series approaches, these covariates can include historical planted areas (Donato & Carraro, 2015; Haile et al., 2014; Iqbal & Babcock, 2018; Ladd & Kongtong, 1979; Parvez et al., 2018). Economic variables are also common, such as commodity prices (Haile et al., 2014, 2016; Iqbal & Babcock, 2018; Ladd & Kongtong, 1979; Parvez et al., 2018), input costs (Donato & Carraro, 2015; Haile et al., 2014, 2016; Iqbal & Babcock, 2018), and price support and loan rates (Donato & Carraro, 2015; Ladd & Kongtong, 1979). Other variables include survey forecasts for the crop of interest and competing crops (Ladd & Kongtong, 1979), expected yields (Iqbal & Babcock, 2018; Ladd & Kongtong, 1979; Parvez et al., 2018), stocks (Parvez et al., 2018), and ethanol-related variables (Parvez et al., 2018).

Models incorporating the impact of weather on planting are less common. Examples include Boyer et al. (2023) and Parvez et al. (2018). Both approaches use total monthly precipitation, ranging from April to July (Parvez et al., 2018) or January to May (Boyer et al., 2023). Both also use air temperature, either the minimum in May and the maximum in June and July (Parvez et al., 2018) or the average air temperatures in April, May, and June (Boyer et al., 2023). The Palmer drought severity index is also used in Parvez et al. (2018). Variables unique to Boyer et al. (2023) are static soil properties, including the water holding capacity, organic matter, and soil loss tolerance. Furthermore, Boyer et al. (2023) model corn and soybean prevented plant areas, as opposed to the total planted areas modeled in the other mentioned sources.

1.2 Objective and Outline

All the past work mentioned use linear models to forecast planted areas. It is of interest to determine whether predictions can be improved with modern machine learning methods. Furthermore, few past works incorporate weather data. For those that do, Parvez et al. (2018) use data that are not available for this application, e.g., weather averages for the entirety of June and July. The work of Parvez et al. (2018) is also limited to North Dakota, which is a small percentage of total U.S. corn area. In addition, Boyer et al. (2023) focus on prevented acreage as opposed to total acreage. Prevented acreage involves not planting at all, so it will not account for other weather induced planting modifications (like switching from corn to soybeans) which could impact the survey accuracy.

The objective of this paper is to use a modern machine learning approach to forecast corn planted area during years with excessive precipitation during the planting season. The county-level regression model combines survey forecasts, historical planted areas, economic data, and weather data with the goal of achieving superior predictive accuracy to the survey alone during resurvey years. The model is meant to provide predictions in mid-June, so that the results may be available during the board process which produces the published June acreage forecasts. Finally, the model should provide high coverage of corn planted area in the United States (e.g., as much of the corn acreage as possible).

In Section 2, the study area and input data are discussed. In Section 3, the model is described. The experiments and results are described in Section 4. Finally, conclusions and future work are discussed in Section 5.

2. Data and Methods

2.1 Study Area

The first decision when developing a model to predict planted area is the geographical resolution. USDA NASS publishes official planted areas at the national, state, and county levels in December. National and state-level forecasts are also provided in March and June. One disadvantage of working at the county level is that USDA NASS does not provide county level survey-based forecasts in March and June. Thus, error may be introduced when down projecting the state level forecasts to the county level. However, higher resolution models may have the advantage when accounting for anomalous weather events because weather events can occur locally within different parts of a state. For this reason, a county-level model was selected.

Corn planted area in the United States varies significantly by county. Figure 1 shows the distribution of county-level planted area for corn, averaged over the years 2013-2022. The average areas planted to corn in a county can range from zero to hundreds of thousands of acres. Much of the corn area is clustered in the midwestern states, although smaller pockets of corn area can be found throughout the country. Iowa and Illinois have first and second largest corn areas, each with over 10 million acres on average.

Figure 1: Average corn planted areas (in acres) by county in the United States.

To select the counties included in the model, the 31 states for which county estimates were produced consistently from 2013-2022 were included (see Figure 2). The included states are Iowa, Illinois, Nebraska, Minnesota, South Dakota, Indiana, Kansas, Wisconsin, Ohio, Missouri, North

Dakota, Texas, Michigan, Kentucky, Pennsylvania, Colorado, New York, North Carolina, Tennessee, Arkansas, Mississippi, Louisiana, Virginia, Maryland, California, Georgia, South Carolina, Oklahoma, Alabama, Delaware, and Washington. These 31 states accounted for an average of 98.5 percent of the total corn acreage between 2013 and 2022; the lowest coverage was 98.4 percent in 2019. Thus, very little corn acreage is lost when focusing on these 31 states. Furthermore, all states that have required resurveying during this time period are included in this 31-state study area.

Figure 2: Study Area: States included are in blue.

The primary focus of this work is on the states that required resurveying in July due to extreme weather conditions which impacted planting. Specifically, 16 states required resurveying between 2013 and 2022 (see Table 1). Of these cases, 13 resurveys occurred in 2019 and three resurveys occurred in 2022, all due to excessive precipitation (USDA-NASS, 2022). Model performance in these states during the resurvey years is of particular importance, as this is when the June Agricultural Survey's accuracy is most likely to be impacted.

Table 1: States Resurveyed due to Excessive Precipitation

Year	State
2019	Iowa
2019	Illinois
2019	Nebraska
2019	Minnesota
2019	Kansas
2019	Indiana
2019	South Dakota
2019	Wisconsin
2019	North Dakota
2019	Missouri
2019	Ohio
2019	Michigan
2019	New York
2022	Minnesota
2022	South Dakota
2022	North Dakota

2.2 Input Data

2.2.1 Historical USDA NASS County Estimates

Every year in February USDA NASS publishes the previous year's corn planted areas at the county level. Most county estimates are available to the public on USDA's Quick Stats website (USDA-NASS, 2023c). Certain counties are withheld from publication if they potentially disclose personally identifiable information of individual farmers. However, these unpublished county estimates are available for use internally to the USDA since 2001. Thus, no data are missing for county estimates for 2001 and later, but some data may be missing prior to 2001. More specifically, any unpublished county estimates not available on Quick Stats prior to 2001 are considered missing data, which is an important consideration for the model selected in Section 3.

2.2.2 USDA NASS Survey Forecasts

In season acreage forecasts can be incorporated into the model using NASS surveys. In particular, the published March ASB forecast is available for inclusion in the June model. Since this forecast is state level, it must be down projected to the county level (Section 2.3.2). The March ASB forecast is publicly available (USDA-NASS, 2023a). Since the goal is to provide the ASB modeled forecasts, the June ASB forecast is not available for use in the model. However, the direct estimates from the June Agricultural Survey are available. Like the March forecast, the June Agricultural Survey direct estimates are only available at the state level, so they must be down projected to the counties (Section 2.3.2). The June Agricultural Survey direct estimates are available internally to the USDA, but are not released to the public.

2.2.3 Economic Data

Daily corn and soybean spot and future prices are included in the model. These price data are obtained from the Chicago Mercantile Exchange via Barchart (Barchart, 2023). Crop insurance prices for corn and soybeans from 2011 to 2022 are obtained using the USDA Risk Management Agency (RMA) price discovery tool (USDA-RMA, 2023). Insurance prices from 2000 to 2010 are obtained using the RMA historical revenue-based crop insurance prices. Finally, insurance prices prior to 2000 are calculated as the average daily Barchart prices using the futures category and cutoff dates provided by the RMA price discovery tool. All data are national values, i.e., they vary between years, but not states and counties.

The last economic data type used is projected beginning stocks and use for corn and soybeans. These data can be obtained via the World Agricultural Supply and Demand Estimates (WASDE) report (USDA-ERS, 2023). The June report is used since it is available relatively early in the month. The stocks and use are also national values, i.e., they only vary temporally.

2.2.4 Weather Data and Plant Dates

All weather-related data are obtained at the county level using the NASS Decision Support System (Guindin et al., 2015; USDA-NASS, 2023b). These data may be queried using a start date and an end date. Weather variables used for this study include total precipitation, air temperature, precipitation percentiles, and air temperature percentiles. Furthermore, critical planting dates (USDA-NASS, 2010) for corn in each state are used for aggregating the weather and economic data during the planting season. These dates separate the typical beginning, most active, and end periods of the planting season. They are typically unique to each state. An example is provided for seven states in Table 2.

Table 2: Planting Periods for Select States

State	Begin	Most Active	End
Illinois	April 14	April 21 – May 23	Jun 5
Indiana	April 20	May 1 – Jun 1	Jun 10
Iowa	April 19	April 25 – May 18	May 26
Kansas	April 5	April 15 – May 15	May 25
Missouri	April 3	April 11 – May 27	Jun 12
Nebraska	April 19	April 27 – May 15	May 21
Ohio	April 18	April 24 – May 24	May 30

2.3 Model Variables

Many of the input data are transformed or summarized prior to use in the model. These transformations are described in this section.

2.3.1 Historical USDA NASS County Estimates

The official county estimates are the prediction objective and therefore are used as the response variable for the regression model. In other words, the response variable is

$$y_{ti} = \mathbf{Area}_{ti}$$

where \mathbf{Area}_{ti} is the planted area in county i for year t . Furthermore, historical planted areas may also be included as predictor variables. In particular, the previous three years of corn planted areas, $y_{(t-1)i}$, $y_{(t-2)i}$, and $y_{(t-3)i}$, are included as predictor variables. Finally, county level 10 year rolling maximum and minimum planted areas are also used as predictors; that is,

$$y_{min,i} = \min(y_{(t-1)i}, y_{(t-2)i}, \dots, y_{(t-10)i})$$

$$y_{max,i} = \max(y_{(t-1)i}, y_{(t-2)i}, \dots, y_{(t-10)i})$$

2.3.2 USDA NASS Survey Forecasts

The survey data provide valuable in season acreage forecasts which can be used as predictor variables. However, as these forecasts are only provided at the state level, they must be down projected to the county level. This is accomplished by creating three predictor variables per survey using the following formulae:

$$z_{1ti}^k = B_{t,s(i)}^k \frac{Y_{(t-1)i}}{\sum_{j \in s(i)} Y_{(t-1)j}}$$

$$z_{2ti}^k = B_{t,s(i)}^k \frac{Y_{(t-2)i}}{\sum_{j \in s(i)} Y_{(t-2)j}}$$

$$z_{3ti}^k = B_{t,s(i)}^k \frac{Y_{(t-3)i}}{\sum_{j \in s(i)} Y_{(t-3)j}}$$

In the above formulae, $B_{t,s(i)}^k$ is the approximate corn planted area for year t in county i 's state, $s(i)$, from the k th source ($k \in (Mar, Jun)$, either the March ASB publication or the June APS survey indications). These transformations assume that the proportion of each county's contribution to the state level corn planted area is related to the past proportions. Three years are used for the possibility of correction when a previous year was an outlier.

2.3.3 Economic Data

Recall from Section 2.2.3 that spot and future prices for corn and soybeans are available daily. Prior to input into the model, the spot and future prices are summarized by averaging the daily values during the end of planting season period for each state. The final economic data used for modeling are normalized ratios between the price and future averages and the crop insurance rates; that is, the price ratio is

$$PR_{ti}^{CS} = \frac{\sum_{d=EPP_{start}(s(i))}^{EPP_{end}(s(i))} \mathcal{P}_{t,d}^C}{\sum_{d=EPP_{start}(s(i))}^{EPP_{end}(s(i))} \mathcal{P}_{t,d}^S}$$

For the corn-soybean price ratio, $PR_{t,s(i)}^{CS}$, the sum is taken over days (d). The sum for county i 's state $s(i)$ starts on the last day of the most active planting period, $EPP_{start}(s(i))$ (see Table 2), and ends at the end of planting the season, $EPP_{end}(s(i))$ (see Table 2). The numerator is the sum of the daily corn prices $\mathcal{P}_{t,d}^C$ for the current year t , while the denominator is the sum of the soybean prices $\mathcal{P}_{t,d}^S$. The futures ratio, $FR_{t,s(i)}^{CS}$, is analogous and defined below, with the prices swapped out for futures \mathcal{F} .

$$FR_{ti}^{CS} = \frac{\sum_{d=EPP_{start}(s(i))}^{EPP_{end}(s(i))} \mathcal{F}_{t,d}^C}{\sum_{d=EPP_{start}(s(i))}^{EPP_{end}(s(i))} \mathcal{F}_{t,d}^S}$$

To incorporate the insurance option, the price and future to insurance ratios are added for corn and soybeans. The explicit formulae are provided below:

$$PIR_{ti}^C = \frac{\sum_{d=EPP_{start}(s(i))}^{EPP_{end}(s(i))} \mathcal{P}_{t,d}^C}{|EPP(s(i))| * I_{t,s(i)}^C}$$

$$PIR_{ti}^S = \frac{\sum_{d=EPP_{start}(s(i))}^{EPP_{end}(s(i))} \mathcal{P}_{t,d}^S}{|EPP(s(i))| * I_{t,s(i)}^S}$$

$$FIR_{ti}^C = \frac{\sum_{d=EPP_{start}(s(i))}^{EPP_{end}(s(i))} \mathcal{F}_{t,d}^C}{|EPP(s(i))| * I_{t,s(i)}^C}$$

$$FIR_{ti}^S = \frac{\sum_{d=EPP_{start}(s(i))}^{EPP_{end}(s(i))} \mathbb{1}_{t,d}^S}{|EPP(s(i))| * I_{t,s(i)}^S}$$

For each quantity above, $|EPP(s(i))|$ is the number of days in the end of planting period for county i 's state $s(i)$ and I refers to the guaranteed insurance price using the RMA price discovery tool (see section 2.2.5).

To summarise the beginning stocks and use data, the stocks to use ratio is calculated. In other words:

$$stur_t^{corn} = \frac{\text{beginning corn stocks}}{\text{projected corn use}}$$

$$stur_t^{soy} = \frac{\text{beginning soybean stocks}}{\text{projected soybean use}}$$

In total, these eight variables represent some of the farmer's economic incentives to choose either between planting corn, switching to soybeans, using the insurance for corn, or using the insurance for soybeans. During a normal year these variables should not matter much as the survey respondents' planting decisions will already be recorded in the survey. However, if planting is delayed due to extreme weather, many of the respondents may have to consider these economic decisions even after recording their planting intentions.

2.3.4 Weather Data

Precipitation totals, precipitation percentiles, temperature averages, and temperature percentiles can be queried directly from the NASS decision support system using a start date and an end date. Variables are created for these quantities at different points in the planting season. Ten variables for various times in the planting season (Table 2) are created from these queries.

Furthermore, as daily data are also available from the NASS decision support system, two additional daily precipitation summaries are created. Let $\vec{r}_{ti}^k = \langle r_{ti1}^k, \dots, r_{tid}^k, \dots, r_{tiD_k}^k \rangle$ be the daily precipitation vector for year t , county i , and planting period k , with length D_k number of days in the planting period. Each element of the vector is a binary indicator of non-zero precipitation. In other words:

$$r_{tid}^k = \begin{cases} 1, \text{ no precipitation in year } t, \text{ county } i, \text{ day } d \text{ planting period } k \\ 0, \text{ otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The first daily summary variable is the proportion of days in each planting period with zero precipitation. In other words:

$$prop_fav_{ti}^k = \frac{\sum_{d=k_{start}}^{k_{end}} r_{tid}^k}{D_k}$$

The index k represents the planting period (see Table 2): the beginning, most active, or end. The second daily summary is the normalized maximum number of consecutive days in each planting period with zero precipitation. To calculate this variable, first consider the zero padded precipitation incidence vector $\vec{q}_{ti}^k = \langle 0, \vec{r}_{ti}^k, 0 \rangle$. Then let l_{ti1}^k be the index of the first zero in \vec{q}_{ti}^k , let l_{ti2}^k be the index of the second zero in \vec{q}_{ti}^k and so on, with $l_{tiE_k}^k$ being the last zero. Then the maximum number of precipitation free days is:

$$max_fav_{ti}^k = \frac{\max(l_{ti2}^k - l_{ti1}^k - 1, l_{ti3}^k - l_{ti2}^k - 1, l_{ti4}^k - l_{ti3}^k - 1, \dots, l_{tiE_k}^k - l_{tiE_{k-1}}^k - 1)}{D_k}$$

The idea is to find the largest available window the farmer can plant during each planting period in Table 2, assuming that days with non-zero precipitation are unfavorable for planting.

2.3.5 Variable Summary

Variables used for modeling (see Table 3) are chosen to represent the historical trend in county corn planted areas, in-season survey-based corn planted area forecasts, county location, economic factors that may impact planting choices, and weather data.

Table 3: Variables Used in Model

Variable Name	Description
y_{ti}	Corn planted in county i , current year (Response variable)
$y_{t-1,i}$	Corn planted in county i , last year
$y_{t-2,i}$	Corn planted in county i , two years ago
$y_{t-3,i}$	Corn planted in county i , three years ago
$y_{min,i}$	Corn planted in county i , ten year minimum
$y_{max,i}$	Corn planted in county i , ten year maximum
z_{1ti}^{Mar}	Down projected March ASB forecast to county i , using last year proportion
z_{2ti}^{Mar}	Down projected March ASB forecast to county i , using two years ago proportion
z_{3ti}^{Mar}	Down projected March ASB forecast to county i , using three years ago proportion
z_{1ti}^{Jun}	Down projected June APS forecast to county i , using last year proportion
z_{2ti}^{Jun}	Down projected June APS forecast to county i , using two years ago proportion
z_{3ti}^{Jun}	Down projected June APS forecast to county i , using three years ago proportion
lat_i	Latitude of county i
lon_i	Longitude of county i
PR_{ti}^{CS}	Corn soybean price ratio in county i
FR_{ti}^{CS}	Corn soybean future ratio in county i
PIR_{ti}^C	Corn spot price to insurance price ratio in county i
PIR_{ti}^S	Soybean spot price to insurance price ratio in county i
FIR_{ti}^C	Corn future price to insurance price ratio in county i
FIR_{ti}^S	Soybean future price to insurance price ratio in county i
$stur_t^{corn}$	Stocks to use ratio: corn
$stur_t^{soy}$	Stocks to use ratio: soybeans
$ppt_tot_i^{beg}$	Precipitation total, beginning planting season in county i
$ppt_pct_i^{beg}$	Precipitation percentile, beginning planting season in county i
$ppt_tot_i^{act}$	Precipitation total, most active planting season in county i
$ppt_pct_i^{act}$	Precipitation percentile, most active planting season in county i
$ppt_tot_i^{end}$	Precipitation total, end planting season in county i
$ppt_pct_i^{end}$	Precipitation percentile, end planting season in county i
$temp_avg_i^{beg}$	Air temperature average, beginning planting season in county i
$temp_pct_i^{beg}$	Air temperature percentile, beginning planting season in county i
$temp_avg_i^{act}$	Air temperature average, most active planting season in county i
$temp_pct_i^{act}$	Air temperature percentile, most active planting season in county i
$temp_avg_i^{end}$	Air temperature average, end planting season in county i
$temp_pct_i^{end}$	Air temperature percentile, end planting season in county i
$prop_fav_{ti}^{beg}$	Proportion of days with zero precipitation, beginning planting season in county i
$max_fav_{ti}^{beg}$	Maximum number of consecutive days with zero precipitation, beginning planting season in county i
$prop_fav_{ti}^{act}$	Proportion of days with zero precipitation, most active planting season in county i
$max_fav_{ti}^{act}$	Maximum number of consecutive days with zero precipitation, most active planting season in county i
$prop_fav_{ti}^{end}$	Proportion of days with zero precipitation, end planting season in county i
$max_fav_{ti}^{end}$	Maximum number of consecutive days with zero precipitation, end planting season in county i

3. Model

3.1 Initial Models

Three initial model types are fit to obtain order of magnitude forecasts based on the expected typical year outcome. This is done because the final official estimates are generally the same order of magnitude as the historical planted areas and survey forecasts, even during years with extreme weather. However, the corn planted area can vary drastically between counties (see Figure 1). As a result, the goal is to obtain the correct order of magnitude, then adjust using the economic and weather data. First, define the initial variable sets:

$$\overline{HIST}_{ti} = \langle y_{t-1,i}, y_{t-2,i}, y_{t-3,i}, y_{min,i}, y_{max,i} \rangle$$

$$\overline{SURV}_{ti} = \langle z_{1ti}^{Mar}, z_{2ti}^{Mar}, z_{3ti}^{Mar}, z_{1ti}^{Jun}, z_{2ti}^{Jun}, z_{3ti}^{Jun} \rangle$$

$$\overline{LOC}_{ti} = \langle lat_i, lon_i \rangle$$

The training start year is selected to be 1989 since that is when the June Agricultural Survey direct estimates are first available.

3.1.1 First Initial Model

The first model is fit using all the data, pooling all 31 states together. In other words, the model is:

$$\hat{y}_{ti1} = g(\overline{HIST}_{ti}, \overline{SURV}_{ti}, \overline{LOC}_{ti})$$

The function g is chosen to minimize the squared error over the entire dataset. In other words, the goal is to choose g to minimize the loss L_{all} :

$$L_{all} = \sum_{t=1989}^{last_year} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{county}} (y_{ti} - \hat{y}_{ti1})^2$$

3.1.2 Second Initial Model

The second model is similar to the first, but a separate model is fit for each state. In other words, 31 separate models, $h_1, \dots, h_s, \dots, h_{31}$, are fit for the $s = 1, \dots, 31$ states; that is, the model for state s is

$$\hat{y}_{ti2} = h_{s(i)}(\overline{HIST}_{ti}, \overline{SURV}_{ti}, \overline{LOC}_{ti})$$

The loss function for state s is

$$L_s = \sum_{i \in s} \sum_{t=1989}^{last_year} (y_{ti} - \hat{y}_{ti2})^2$$

Fitting a separate model for each state allows for potential state level heterogeneity, considering survey sample sizes and accuracies differ by state.

3.1.2 Third Initial Model

The third model attempts to correct for the wide range in corn acreage magnitude (see Figure 1) by separating counties by expected planted area. The idea is for counties with small anticipated planted areas to be modeled in a different group than those with large anticipated planted areas (see Table 4 for the groups).

Table 4: County Projected Planted Area Groups

Group	Bounds
1	$y_{t-1,i} = 0$
2	$0 < y_{t-1,i} \leq 200$
3	$200 < y_{t-1,i} \leq 500$
4	$500 < y_{t-1,i} \leq 1,000$
5	$1,000 < y_{t-1,i} \leq 2,000$
6	$2,000 < y_{t-1,i} \leq 4,000$
7	$4,000 < y_{t-1,i} \leq 7,000$
8	$7,000 < y_{t-1,i} \leq 11,000$
9	$11,000 < y_{t-1,i} \leq 18,000$
10	$18,000 < y_{t-1,i} \leq 29,000$
11	$29,000 < y_{t-1,i} \leq 45,000$
12	$45,000 < y_{t-1,i} \leq 70,000$
13	$70,000 < y_{t-1,i} \leq 100,000$
14	$y_{t-1,i} > 100,000$

Given the groups in Table 4, the third model is similar to the first and second but separated by group. In other words, 14 separate models, $m_1, \dots, m_g, \dots, m_{14}$, are fit for the $g = 1, \dots, 14$ groups. The model for group g is

$$\hat{y}_{ti3} = m_g(\overline{HIST}_{ti}, \overline{SURV}_{ti}, \overline{STAT}_{ti})$$

The loss function for group g is

$$L_g = \sum_{i \in g} \sum_{t=1989}^{last_year} (y_{ti} - \hat{y}_{ti3})^2$$

3.2 Final Model

The predictions from the three initial models are combined with the economic and weather data to fit the final model at the state level Consider the variable sets below:

$$\overline{ECON}_{ti} = \langle PR_{ti}^{CS}, FR_{ti}^{CS}, PIR_{ti}^C, FIR_{ti}^C, PIR_{ti}^S, FIR_{ti}^S, stur_t^{corn}, stur_t^{soy} \rangle$$

$$\overline{W}_{ti1} = \langle ppt_tot_i^{beg}, ppt_pct_i^{beg}, temp_avg_i^{beg}, temp_pct_i^{beg}, prop_fav_{ti}^{beg}, max_fav_{ti}^{beg} \rangle$$

$$\overline{W}_{ti2} = \langle ppt_tot_i^{act}, ppt_pct_i^{act}, temp_avg_i^{act}, temp_pct_i^{act}, prop_fav_{ti}^{act}, max_fav_{ti}^{act} \rangle$$

$$\overline{W}_{ti3} = \langle ppt_tot_i^{end}, ppt_pct_i^{end}, temp_avg_i^{end}, temp_pct_i^{end}, prop_fav_{ti}^{end}, max_fav_{ti}^{end} \rangle$$

Separate models, $f_1, \dots, f_s, \dots, f_{31}$, are fit for the $s = 1, \dots, 31$ states; that is, the model for state s is

$$\hat{y}_{ti} = f_s(\hat{y}_{ti1}, \hat{y}_{ti2}, \hat{y}_{ti3}, \overline{STAT}_{ti}, \overline{ECON}_{ti}, \overline{W}_{ti1}, \overline{W}_{ti2}, \overline{W}_{ti3})$$

The loss function for state s is

$$L_s^{Final} = \sum_{i \in s} \sum_{t=1989}^{last_year} (y_{ti} - \hat{y}_{ti})^2$$

3.3 Model Parameters

In principle any machine learning algorithm can be used to minimize the squared error loss. This application involves missing data, so gradient boosting models are ideal. Gradient boosting handles missing data internally, not requiring an imputation preprocessing step by the user (Ke et al., 2017). Furthermore, gradient boosting has been shown to perform well on larger datasets with skewed, heavy tailed feature distributions (McElfresh et al., 2023). These characteristics match well with this application as corn planted areas tend to be right skewed and the data set is relatively large. The specific gradient boosting method used in this task is LightGBM (Ke et al., 2017).

Like most machine learning models, LightGBM has a variety of tuning parameters. Tuning parameter selection is conducted via five-fold cross validation on the training data. The best tuning parameters minimizing the average squared error on the holdout sets are used to train the final model. A range of tuning parameters are considered (see Table 5). Parameters not included in Table 5 are set to the LightGBM defaults. Note that the training procedure is the same for the three initial models in Section 3.1 and the final model in Section 3.2.

Table 5: Tuning Parameters

Tuning Parameter	Options Tested
feature_fraction	0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1
bagging_fraction	0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1
max_bin	255
num_leaves	32, 64, 128, 256, 512
max_depth	-1
reg_alpha	0
reg_lambda	0
boosting	goss
nrounds	5000
early_stopping_rounds	50

4. Experiment and Results

4.1 Experimental Setup

To assess model quality, the entire procedure is evaluated over a ten-year period, 2013-2022. To obtain a realistic error assessment, the predictions for each year are entirely based on historical training data. In other words, the 2013 model is trained on data from 1989-2012, the 2014 model is trained on data from 1989-2013, and so on, with the 2022 model being trained on data from 1989-2021. The modeled predictions are compared to the June ASB publication, and each are evaluated with respect to the official December acreages. The evaluation is carried out at the total acreage (of the 31 states under consideration) as well as the state level. The metric for evaluation is percent error. The formula for percent error is:

$$\text{percent error} = 100 * \frac{|\text{approximation} - \text{true}|}{\text{true}}$$

In this case the approximation is either the model prediction or the June ASB forecast. The true value is the official December published value.

4.1 Results, Overall Acreage

The results for the total acreage forecast over the study area (31 states) are provided in Table 6. The ground truth column refers to the December official planted acreage while the June column refers to the June published ASB forecast.

Table 6: Results: Total Planted Area, 2013-2022

Year	Ground Truth	June Published	Model Forecast	June Percent Error	Model Percent Error
2013	93,980,000	95,975,000	94,077,904	2.12	0.10
2014	89,305,000	90,355,000	90,277,869	1.18	1.09
2015	86,825,000	87,675,000	86,068,496	0.98	0.87
2016	92,675,000	92,790,000	91,266,997	0.12	1.52
2017	88,880,000	89,580,000	87,990,417	0.79	1.00
2018	87,560,000	87,810,000	86,552,464	0.29	1.15
2019	88,335,000	90,350,000	88,076,940	2.28	0.29
2020	89,255,000	90,645,000	91,202,591	1.56	2.18
2021	91,975,000	91,275,000	90,773,713	0.76	1.31
2022	87,315,000	88,620,000	87,708,408	1.49	0.45
Average	x	x	x	1.16	1.00
Maximum	x	x	x	2.28	2.18

On average, the model forecast and June ASB forecast are close, with the model forecast being slightly better in terms of average and maximum error. The ASB forecast tends to do better in the more recent, normal years while the model outperforms during the two resurvey years, 2019 and 2022. These conclusions are not surprising, as the ASB forecast is known to be very accurate during normal years, while the purpose of the model was to correct the forecast during outlier years.

The results for the total resurveyed acreages are provided in Table 7. The model performance on total acreage is much better during the resurvey years overall. In 2019 the model forecast is about twice as accurate as the June ASB forecast while almost six times as accurate in 2022. The results demonstrate that model-based forecasts are promising for use during outlier planting years, at least for forecasting acreage totals over large land areas (see Table 7).

Table 7: Results: Total Resurveyed Area

Year	Ground Truth	June Published	Model Forecast	June Percent Error	Model Percent Error
2019	73,970,000	76,420,000	75,155,463	3.31	1.60
2022	16,700,000	17,200,000	16,785,171	2.99	0.51

4.2 Results, By State

The results by state are provided in Table 8 for the 31 states individually in the study area. The average planted areas are the average ground truth acreages for each state taken from 2013-2022. The average errors are the average percent errors for each state from the ASB forecast and model, also taken over the evaluation years 2013-2022. The states are sorted from highest average corn planted area to lowest.

Table 8: Results: Average by State

State	Average Planted Area	Average Error June Published	Average Error Model Forecast
Iowa	13,410,000	1.49	1.12
Illinois	11,300,000	1.62	1.35
Nebraska	9,745,000	1.67	1.84
Minnesota	8,150,000	1.73	1.72
South Dakota	5,515,000	4.83	7.03
Indiana	5,485,000	2.73	2.26
Kansas	5,225,000	3.01	5.68
Wisconsin	3,965,000	2.25	2.60
Ohio	3,490,000	2.77	3.41
Missouri	3,425,000	3.53	3.99
North Dakota	3,192,000	7.07	7.70
Texas	2,350,000	5.80	9.71
Michigan	2,345,000	5.72	3.92
Kentucky	1,461,000	2.64	3.21
Pennsylvania	1,379,000	3.35	4.84
Colorado	1,343,000	4.39	5.17
New York	1,072,000	5.21	4.37
North Carolina	913,000	2.72	4.34
Tennessee	863,000	8.25	7.66
Arkansas	687,000	6.24	10.07
Mississippi	611,000	7.56	11.62
Louisiana	516,000	6.00	7.59
Virginia	500,500	5.87	5.07
Maryland	470,000	3.71	5.54
California	455,000	5.18	6.69
Georgia	393,500	7.98	9.40
South Carolina	349,500	3.61	3.53
Oklahoma	348,000	5.56	14.61
Alabama	302,000	4.28	3.82
Delaware	175,500	4.00	4.66
Washington	174,500	9.93	11.08

In terms of number of states, the ASB forecasts tends to perform better over the 10-year period. More specifically, there are 21 states where the ASB forecast has a lower average error. This is not unexpected as state scale predictions are higher resolution and more error prone. Furthermore, the ASB forecast is at its best during normal years, which make up the majority of 2013-2022 (only 13 states in 2019 and 3 states in 2022 are outliers). Finally, the down projection step in Section 2.3.2 will likely introduce errors which can accumulate. These errors may be counteracted by the

inclusion of auxiliary data during outlier years but are likely to add too much error during normal years when the ASB forecast is at its best.

Acreage results for the resurveyed states are provided in Table 9 below. As expected, the conclusion of Table 9, for resurvey cases, is the opposite as that found in Table 8 for normal cases. The modeled forecasts dominate in the resurveyed cases, providing lower error in 12 of the 16 resurvey cases. Interestingly, in three of the four cases where the model underperforms, one occurs when the ASB forecast is perfect (Wisconsin, 2019). The other two occur in the only two examples where the final acreage *increases* from the June ASB forecast (Nebraska 2019 and Kansas 2019). Increases are unexpected during excessive precipitation events, so future work is needed to examine these two states more closely. Regardless, the results of Table 9 demonstrate that model-based estimates are promising for use during outlier planting years, even at the state level.

Table 9: Results: Average by State

Year	State	Ground Truth	June Published	Model Forecast	June Percent Error	Model Percent Error
2019	Iowa	13,500,000	13,600,000	13,474,857	0.74	0.19
2019	Illinois	10,500,000	11,000,000	10,720,304	4.76	2.10
2019	Nebraska	10,100,000	10,000,000	9,602,627	0.99	4.92
2019	Minnesota	7,800,000	8,000,000	7,960,583	2.56	2.06
2019	Kansas	6,400,000	5,900,000	5,687,141	7.81	11.14
2019	Indiana	5,000,000	5,500,000	5,363,396	10.00	7.27
2019	South Dakota	4,350,000	4,800,000	4,821,027	10.34	10.83
2019	Wisconsin	3,800,000	3,800,000	3,921,153	0.00	3.19
2019	North Dakota	3,500,000	3,700,000	3,603,723	5.71	2.96
2019	Missouri	3,200,000	3,400,000	3,382,066	6.25	5.69
2019	Ohio	2,800,000	3,300,000	3,246,747	17.86	15.96
2019	Michigan	2,000,000	2,300,000	2,273,476	15.00	13.67
2019	New York	1,020,000	1,120,000	1,098,364	9.80	7.68
2022	Minnesota	8,000,000	8,300,000	7,972,664	3.75	0.34
2022	South Dakota	5,750,000	5,900,000	5,875,114	2.61	2.18
2022	North Dakota	2,950,000	3,000,000	2,937,393	1.69	0.43

5. Conclusion and Future Work

In this study a county-level model was proposed to forecast corn planted area in June for 31 states. The model used machine learning with weather and economic information to adjust June Agricultural Survey-based forecasts in years with excessive precipitation. The model performed well with respect to the June ASB forecast during resurvey years, improving total acreage accuracy as well as state level accuracy in most cases. The model was less competitive during normal years, with roughly equivalent total acreage accuracy and generally lower state level accuracy.

Future work includes improving the quality of state level model predictions during normal years. Furthermore, exploring the causes for some states to increase their planted acreage during years with seemingly adverse weather conditions would also be useful.

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